

Course Contents and Schedules

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1 Program Structure

The SPACE doctoral school was structured around three courses, each lasting one week and consisting of up to twenty lectures. The courses offered both theoretical and practical lectures, as reported in the following sections. Lastly, course projects were assigned to students wishing to take a final exam. The three courses were designed to provide participants with fundamental concepts, approaches, and technologies in space software engineering, viewed from the perspectives of robotics, digital twins, and AI, when applied in the contexts of space applications, space manufacturing, and satellites.

1.1 Digital Twins for Space Manufacturing and Satellites

The course content mainly focused on the exploitation of digital twins technologies for different purposes, ranging from runtime monitoring, real-time simulation, co-simulation, optimization of manufacturing processes, to diagnostics, and autonomous operations. The lectures covered a variety of contexts, including systems engineering, aerospace applications, in-orbit services, and teleoperation of industrial robot arms, among others. Additionally, the course offered two keynotes. The first was about Twinning for and by Systems Engineering and presented the “twinning paradigm” for engineering cyber-physical systems, with a focus on modelling and simulation concepts. The second, instead, was given by a speaker from ESA and presented the ESA Digital Twin Earth, namely the Digital Twin Earth programmes

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that are aimed at transforming traditional Earth Observation into predictive Earth Observation and corresponding future scenarios. A complete view of the program is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Digital Twins for Space Manufacturing and Satellites: Course Content and Schedule

Day	Lecture Title	Lecture description and concepts covered
1	Twinning for and by Systems Engineering	After providing a historical overview of the term Digital Twin, the lecture introduces the paradigm of ‘twinning,’ with a focus on modeling and simulation concepts.
1	(An Introduction to) Systems Engineering & Requirements Modelling for Testing and Run-time Monitoring	The lecture analyzes Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) as a systematic approach to managing complex engineering projects.
1	An Introduction to Equation-based Object-Oriented Modelling of Cyber-Physical Systems with Modelica & Twinning in Practice: the Gantry Crane case	The first lecture introduces Equation-Based Object-Oriented languages. It also presents Modelica as a concrete and widely used example. This is followed by a practical demonstration of modeling a real small-scale system available in the classroom—specifically, an overhead crane, a mechatronic system composed of mechanical, electrical, and software components.
2	An Introduction to Co-Simulation & Recap of “Twinning for and by Systems Engineering”	The lectures analyze the basic concepts of co-simulation and show how to perform co-simulations according to the Functional Mockup Interface (FMI) standard.
2	Intelligence-at-the-Edge for Space-Air-Ground Integrated Networks	The lecture analyzes the domain of Edge Intelligence within Space-Air-Ground Integrated Networks (SAGIN).
2	Engineering Digital Twins: Connecting Physical and Digital Worlds for Intelligent Ecosystems	The lecture examines the architectural requirements related to the life cycle of digital twins, from conceptual design to implementation, highlighting critical aspects concerning interoperability, scalability, and adaptability.
2	Leveraging Extended Reality and Digital Twins in Aerospace Application	The lecture provides an overview of how digital twins can leverage XR approaches in different product life cycle phases. It also explores key aspects of using augmented reality with digital twins.
3	Leonardo Electro-Optical Payload Digital Twin Project & Use of Digital Twin in the sizing and development of Robot Arm for In-Orbiting Service domain	The two lectures present the Electro-Optical Payload Digital Twin Project developed by Leonardo. In addition, the second lecture addresses In-Orbit Servicing (IOS) missions, which are fundamental for the maintenance, repair, and refueling of satellites already in orbit. The project of the Italian Space Agency, led by Thales Alenia Space with Leonardo responsible for the robotic system, is presented. In particular, the Digital Twin of the robotic arm, developed by Leonardo to support complex operations in space, is illustrated.
3	Development of Full Digital Power Control Unit (PCU) for Satellite Electronic Power System (EPS)	The lecture presents a modular Digital Twin for Electrical Power Systems (EPS), which are fundamental for managing and conditioning electrical power on board satellites.
4	ESA Digital Twin Earth	The lecture analyzes two Digital Twin Earth programs, which aim to transform traditional Earth observation—capable of providing information on the past and present state of the planet—into predictive observation, able to deliver insights into future scenarios.
4	Optimization of Manufacturing Processes through AI and Digital Twins	The lecture presents a systematic approach to optimizing manufacturing processes using AI algorithms and Digital Twins. It also includes a demo of a digital twin of an industrial plant using Tecnomatix Plant Simulation.
4	Digital Twins: Beyond the Surface - Engineering Foundations and Future Frontiers	The lecture delves into the engineering foundations of Digital Twins, moving beyond the theoretical concept to explore essential tools and methodologies for their development. Topics addressed include control theory, Model Predictive Control (MPC), Model-Driven Engineering (MDE), advanced simulation, and the integration of AI/ML techniques. Particular attention is devoted to practical challenges, such as model accuracy, real-time data management, and cybersecurity, to provide an interdisciplinary and concrete perspective on using Digital Twins in the space sector and beyond.
4	Digital Twins for Teleoperation of Industrial Robot Arm	The lecture introduces the design and implementation of a digital twin-based teleoperation system capable of mapping human arm movements onto an industrial robotic arm in real time through sensors.
5	Digital Twins for Space: Advancing Monitoring, Diagnostics, and Autonomous Operations	The lecture illustrates the use of Digital Twins for advanced monitoring and predictive diagnostics of space platforms such as satellites, rovers, and stations. By integrating DTs into operational systems, traditional monitoring evolves into a model-based adaptive approach, enhancing early fault detection, mitigation strategies, and operational autonomy.
5	Digital Twin Earth solutions from Space	The lecture discusses how using high-resolution satellite data, combined with advanced Artificial Intelligence models, enables the creation of a dynamic virtual representation of the Earth. It also analyzes practical applications in climate monitoring, natural resource management, and disaster prevention.
5	Model-Driven Engineering of Digital Twins for Manufacturing and Digital Twin Software Architectures	The lecture explores how modeling enables the management of long-duration system complexity and how fundamental function models of cyber-physical systems in manufacturing can automatically generate digital twins.
5	Unlocking the Potential of Digital Twins	The lecture analyzes the fundamentals of digital twins, highlighting recent contributions from the Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) community and discussing the main challenges that need to be addressed to realize the vision of digital twins fully.

1.2 Artificial Intelligence for Aerospace

The course content mainly focused on AI for Earth Observation (EO), onboard data analysis, safety analysis, anomaly detection, and remote sensing. Some lectures discussed the timely topics of trustworthiness, explainability, and sustainability in AI for space applications. The course offered one keynote, titled AI and the infinite: the intersection of AI and Space ventures, and an additional guest lecture on Space Economy given by an economist from Eurospace, and giving an economist perspective on space markets and industrial structures, with a focus on infrastructure development and financing, and a data-based analysis of major trends affecting the space sector in the past decades. A complete view of the program is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Artificial Intelligence for Aerospace: Course Content and Schedule

Day	Lecture Title	Lecture description and concepts covered
1	AI and the infinite: the intersection of AI and Space ventures	The lecture presents examples of using AI in the space sector, particularly for mission planning and operations such as autonomous navigation. It then discusses AI/ML applications in space exploration and the related challenges researchers and professionals face.
1	Trustworthiness and explainability in AI for Space application	The lecture highlights the importance of ensuring the reliability of AI in space applications such as autonomous navigation and data analysis. It emphasizes that defining metrics based on explainable mechanisms is essential to increase the transparency, interpretability, and accountability of decisions made by complex models, ensuring consistency with mission objectives and reducing operational risks.
1	AI/ML for safety-critical software: the case of the space domain	The lecture discusses the need for structured methodologies to assess the performance and reliability of AI models in aerospace systems. It addresses tools for alignment with system requirements, explainability, traceability, and validation challenges, and the role of evolving standards. Through practical examples of innovative AI architectures, it proposes a roadmap for the responsible and safe adoption of AI in critical aerospace domains.
1	New generation of virtualization infrastructure in space	The lecture shows how containers (Docker) enable the isolation of critical applications, enhancing space missions' security and operational flexibility. It also examines workload sizing, performance monitoring, and integration with hybrid cloud systems.
2	Introduction to AI in Space Safety and Sustainability & Applying AI to Mission Design: Working Groups	The lectures explore the role of AI in the future of space safety and sustainability, with particular focus on collision avoidance, debris management, and autonomous decision-making in satellite operations. In addition, participants are involved in the design of missions that leverage AI to ensure sustainability.
2	Introduction to Machine Learning for Onboard Data Analysis in Earth Observation & Hands-On: Implementing a Neural Network-Based Classification Algorithm	The lectures provide an overview of machine learning techniques for directly processing data in real time on board satellites. In addition, participants are involved in implementing a neural network to classify data from Earth observation activities.
2	A trillion dollars economy? Space economy fundamentals, trends, and externalities	The lecture examines the space industries and markets from an economic perspective, with particular attention to the financing and development of infrastructures. It also analyzes the sources and methods for measuring the economic return of space activities, highlighting the notions of market and externalities.
3	Automated testing of deep neural networks for computer vision tasks in space & Supporting safety analysis of Deep Neural Networks through failure explanation	The lectures provide an overview of recent research methods that combine simulators with evolutionary search algorithms to identify the worst-case scenarios for Deep Neural Networks during testing.
3	Analysis of Perception Neural Networks via Vision-Language Models	The lecture provides an overview of ongoing research that leverages Multi-modal Vision-Language Models for formal analysis and monitoring requirements expressed in natural language.
4	AI for Earth Observation (AI4EO) in action: Insights and Innovations & Building a Cloud-Based Downstream Earth Observation Application with WASDI	The lectures analyze the strengths and limitations of AI4EO applications. In addition, participants are guided in implementing an EO application using the tools previously introduced and provided by WASDI.
4	An Overview of Anomaly Detection for Time Series & A deep dive into time series anomaly detection evaluation measures	The lectures explore strategies for automatically selecting appropriate methods for anomaly detection in a given time series.
5	Automating spaceborne Earth observation data exploitation through deep learning: current status and future perspectives	The lecture provides an overview of the main deep learning-based solutions for EO activities, including object detection, classification, data preparation, and land cover classification.
5	ORBIT: Web application for research and planning of potential satellite acquisitions for detection	The lecture introduces ORBIT, a web application that searches for and plans potential satellite acquisitions for detection purposes. Participants use the ORBIT tool to conduct searches with acquisitions from major satellites over selected geographical areas.
5	Use of high-resolution remote sensing data for mapping the extent of water reservoirs and flooded areas: basic principles and applications	The lecture illustrates the basic principles of remote sensing over aquatic surfaces using optical and SAR data. It also presents several applications carried out in collaboration with the Department of Civil Protection.
5	Downscaling satellite precipitation fields using convolutional neural networks	The lecture analyzes the potential of downscaling techniques based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to increase the spatial resolution of satellite-derived precipitation data. In particular, it examines CNN model architectures, their training processes on different datasets, and their ability to capture complex spatial patterns and features within precipitation areas.